

Relationship of Population Configuration with Enrollment of Children at Primary Level of District Bannu

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Abstract: *The Problem under study was the relationship of population composition with enrollment of children at primary level. The study was significant because we can make forecasting of educational plans keeping in view the relationship. All the Primary School of the District Bannu was included in the population for the study. The sample was 05 Urban Male School, 05 Urban Female School, 05 Rural Male School, and 05 Rural Female School. The research instrument was a questionnaire. Through this questionnaire data was collected regarding schools from 2013 to 2019 in different classes. The null hypothesis that there is no relationship between the population composition and enrollment was tested. The result shows that the correlation between the enrollment and the population growth is 0.98. It is high correlation which indicates the strong relationship between the number of enrollment of student and population*

Key Words: Relationship, Population Configuration, Enrollment, Children, Primary Level

Introduction

Socrates defines education as, “Education is the mean that helps in searching the truth. Truth is hidden in the minds of human being and they should be aware of that. Rousseau: Education is the development of human nature in free environment. John Dewey: “education is a process of living through a continuous reconstruction of experiences”. It means that education is the development of the whole personality of an individual. In Pakistan there are four levels of education. Primary education, Secondary education, College and University education. Primary education is the first stage of compulsory education. It is preceded by preschool or nursery education and is followed by secondary education.

Increasing Population and Standard of Life. (it’s Positive & Negative Aspects)

[Iqbal \(2017\)](#) Pakistan is a developing country & its whole population is approximately (16,000,000) sixteen crores. Now the population of Pakistan is increasing very rapidly. If we imagine about increasing population, we feel hesitation but it has some positive aspects too. Which is the following: -

The foremost positive aspect of increasing population is that it brings power and strength. About it we have a wise-saying that “majority is authority”. Now in our country those people who are in majority they have well and stable back. But those who are in minority they consider inferior. So, we can say that strength and power can be brought through majority that why increasing population is considered beneficent ([Ahmad Maqbool, 2006](#)).

Second is also positive aspect of increasing population that the people who are dominant in majority are well acquainted. Everyone knows them well because of their cost and spreading influence. But those who are less not so well known. That’s why we many say that increasing population leads us to a good name and fame ([Katozi Ali Murad, 2005](#)).

Third, increasing population has a very important aspect because our religion permits us to increase population so that to increase religious color in the world. Now if we go through according to the teachings of Islam we must abolish family planning because it is a negation of our religion and try to increase our population ([Iqbal, 2017](#)). Next, the more we increase the more we will progress. If we our

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population increases, we will have health facility because more of the people will enter in a health department. Many of the people will cultivate agriculture and bring food prosperity etc. (Tanvir, 2004).

According to educational survey of Abadiat ([Ministry of Education, 1999](#)) population has negative aspects which are the following: -

- First of all, we have our health problem. It is a negative aspect of increasing population. Because in our country there is a lack of physicians and hospitals, if our population increases day by day then we will face difficulty in providing health case to our patients. So, we should adopt a well family planning according to our resources.
- Secondly, it is another negative aspect of increasing population which is economical problem. Our country Pakistan is not so stable economically to provide financial to each and every individual whether in ease of jobs or education etc. that's why our population should be balance to our economy. Otherwise we will face difficulty.
- Another negative impact of increasing population has on our education. It can affect our education because the inhabitants of our country are economically weak. They can't afford more expenditure because their income is small than their outcome. That's why if they increase their population, they will be unable to provide a proper education to their children. That's why I suggest that everyone should go parallel with their expenditure.
- Next, increasing population leads us to a lack of confidence. They destroy our determination and leads our children to confusion because in an increasing population. Children have no their childhood. They can't find a thing for which they demand. So it should be a balanced one because it is the cry and demand of the day.

Bad Effects of Population Increase on the Education

In Pakistan population growth is, Problem Number one of Pakistan. Higher growth rates of population have very serious effects on various phases of a country. The major reason of higher education rate of developed countries is its decrease in eighteen years old population ([Ministry of education 1992](#)). One of the effects of higher population growth rates is on the quality of education. That as a country's overall development and living standard depends upon education, the higher quality of education leads the nation towards the development and prosperity. But the higher population rates effect the quality of education and the people have to substitute the quality or quantity. Because it becomes more difficult to advice the quality education due to limited resources. Suppose a father who has two children can education them easily and if a father has six children then he will have to face various problems due to which he could not educate well and they become a burden on him. So, we can compare counties population with its available resources. If country population is growing rapidly, obviously it will affect the quality of education ([Baker, 2009](#))

Problem Statement

The problem under study was “to investigate the relationship of population composition with enrollment of children at primary level.”

Research Objectives

- i) To know the relationship between male and female students' enrollment in primary school.
- ii) To know the difference of enrollment between rural and urban primary schools.
- iii) To find out the relationship b/w population composition and enrollment at primary level.

Significance of the Study

This study was significant due to the following reasons.

- i) This study tells as about the male and female student's enrollment in the primary schools of the district Bannu due to which we can easily plane for the education of these children. Also, the

strength of enrollment helps in the decision-making process for the education for the administration.

- ii) This study also tells us about the rich and poor students enrollment in the primary schools of the district Bannu, which is very helpful information, because on the behalf of this information we can advertise the education in those areas of the district and in those stratus of the district where there is less motivation of male and female students towards the education. Mostly the poor peoples can't effort the education for their children, so this study not only highlights such problems but also helps in the education of for flung areas of the district.
- iii) This study tells us about the education level of rural and urban areas, also about the male and female children. Mostly the people in this district don't send their female children in school, so this study in a type of effort to motivate such parents towards education.

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: there is no significance difference of enrollment between male and female students in primary schools.

H₀₂: there is no significance difference of enrollment between rural and urban primary schools.

H₀₃: there is no relationship between population compositions with enrollment.

Limitation

There was no such instrument for the collection of record from the primary schools so the researcher developed questionnaires were used for the collection of data. Also the schools can't maintain the commutative record of each and every student, so only available record was used for the purpose.

Delimitation

Following was delimitation of the study.

Study was delimited to ten male and ten female public schools in district Bannu.

Research Methodology

Research Population

All the Primary School of the District Bannu was included in the population for the study.

Research Sample

Following sample was used for the research purpose in District Bannu.

1. Urban Male School	=	05	
2. Urban Female School	=	05	
3. Rural Male School	=	05	
4. Rural Female School	=	<u>05</u>	
Total	=	20	

Research Instrument

The research instrument was a questionnaire. Through this questionnaire data was collected regarding schools from 2013 to 2019 in different classes.

Research Procedure

Keeping in view the experts views the questionnaire was developed. The researcher personally visited the schools and distributed the questionnaire. The data thus collected in questionnaire was arranged in the form of tables. Then for the purpose of data analysis Co-efficient of correlation was used as a statistical tool.

Statistical Analysis

Co-efficient of correlation was used as statistical technique.

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Table 1. School GGPS Ghazimarjan (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	6	9	11	12	15	17	18
2 nd class	5	8	10	13	16	18	20
3 rd class	7	10	12	14	17	19	21
4 th class	6	8	10	13	15	17	19
5 th class	4	7	9	12	14	16	18
Total	28	42	52	64	77	87	96

Table 2. School GGPS Awalzoman (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	9	11	14	16	13	15	17
2 nd class	8	9	12	14	15	16	18
3 rd class	10	12	15	13	14	17	19
4 th class	12	14	16	19	15	13	18
5 th class	11	13	15	18	20	19	21
Total	50	59	72	80	77	80	93

Table 3. School GGPS Mir Salam Khan (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	8	10	13	15	18	21	24
2 nd class	10	12	15	17	20	23	25
3 rd class	9	11	14	16	18	20	22
4 th class	7	10	15	17	19	22	24
5 th class	6	9	12	14	17	20	23
Total	40	52	69	79	92	106	118

Table 4. School GGPS Bandar Kala (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	5	7	10	12	14	17	19
2 nd class	4	6	9	11	13	15	18
3 rd class	6	8	10	13	15	17	20
4 th class	5	7	9	11	13	15	19
5 th class	4	6	8	12	15	17	20
Total	24	34	46	59	70	81	96

Table 5. School GGPS Jandukhel (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	6	8	10	13	15	17	19
2 nd class	5	7	9	11	13	15	17
3 rd class	5	8	11	13	15	18	20

4 th class	4	7	9	12	14	16	18
5 th class	5	8	10	13	15	17	19
Total	25	38	49	62	72	83	93

Table 6. School GPS Gul Bazar (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	13	19	27	33	47	49	58
2 nd class	15	20	26	31	38	45	60
3 rd class	13	18	25	30	37	40	45
4 th class	16	21	27	32	42	50	55
5 th class	20	28	35	43	47	51	56
Total	77	106	140	169	205	235	274

Table 7. School GPS Ayaz Khan (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	15	20	24	31	37	43	50
2 nd class	17	21	26	30	38	44	52
3 rd class	20	25	29	36	41	37	43
4 th class	18	21	25	32	37	42	49
5 th class	14	18	23	26	30	36	42
Total	84	105	127	155	183	202	236

Table 8. School GPS Alamdin (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	11	20	27	33	40	48	55
2 nd class	7	13	20	27	35	40	47
3 rd class	10	16	22	30	37	44	52
4 th class	12	20	26	21	19	23	31
5 th class	15	18	16	13	11	9	7
Total	55	87	111	124	142	164	192

Table 9. School GPS Laotykala (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	16	20	24	27	30	28	33
2 nd class	19	22	25	28	32	35	38
3 rd class	21	24	27	30	33	30	35
4 th class	23	26	30	34	37	40	43
5 th class	25	28	32	35	40	38	41
Total	104	120	138	154	172	171	190

Table 10. School GPS Azim Kala (Rural)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	19	24	29	34	39	44	49
2 nd class	16	19	23	28	33	36	42
3 rd class	14	20	24	27	31	35	40

4 th class	17	21	25	29	27	32	36
5 th class	18	22	26	24	28	31	35
Total	84	106	127	142	158	178	202

Table 11. School GGPS NO 1 City (Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	13	16	18	21	24	27	30
2 nd class	11	14	16	17	15	20	22
3 rd class	13	15	17	21	24	27	31
4 th class	15	17	19	23	26	29	32
5 th class	14	16	20	22	25	30	34
Total	66	78	90	104	114	133	149

Table 12. School GGPS NO 2 City (Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	12	14	17	19	21	23	26
2 nd class	11	13	16	18	20	22	25
3 rd class	10	12	15	17	19	21	24
4 th class	9	11	14	16	18	22	25
5 th class	8	11	13	17	19	23	24
Total	50	61	75	87	97	111	124

Table 13. School GGPS NO 3 City (Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	13	15	17	20	23	25	27
2 nd class	12	14	16	19	22	24	26
3 rd class	10	13	15	17	20	22	25
4 th class	9	12	14	16	19	21	24
5 th class	8	11	13	15	17	19	23
Total	52	65	75	85	101	111	125

Table 14. School GGPS NO 4 City (Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	14	16	19	22	25	28	32
2 nd class	12	14	17	20	23	25	27
3 rd class	11	13	15	18	20	23	26
4 th class	9	12	14	17	19	22	25
5 th class	8	10	13	16	18	20	24
Total	54	65	78	93	105	118	134

Table 15. School GGPS Mandon (Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	15	17	20	22	25	27	30
2 nd class	14	16	17	20	22	25	27
3 rd class	11	14	16	18	20	22	25

4 th class	9	12	15	17	19	21	24
5 th class	7	10	12	15	17	20	23
Total	56	69	80	92	103	115	129

Table 16. School GPS NO 1 City (Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	20	26	32	37	42	50	60
2 nd class	22	28	34	40	45	51	62
3 rd class	19	25	30	36	41	48	55
4 th class	24	29	34	43	50	56	63
5 th class	106	133	162	192	219	254	296

Table 17. School GPS NO 2 City (Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	19	24	29	34	40	45	52
2 nd class	18	23	28	33	39	44	50
3 rd class	16	20	25	30	35	41	49
4 th class	15	19	26	31	37	43	51
5 th class	13	18	24	29	34	40	45
Total	81	104	132	157	185	213	247

Table 18. School GPS NO 3 City(Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	20	24	27	31	36	40	46
2 nd class	19	22	26	30	35	39	43
3 rd class	17	20	25	29	34	38	41
4 th class	15	18	23	26	29	34	40
5 th class	13	17	21	25	30	33	38
Total	84	101	122	141	164	184	208

Table 19. School GPS Tehsil Street City (Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	18	22	25	29	33	36	41
2 nd class	16	20	24	30	34	37	40
3 rd class	15	19	23	29	38	45	50
4 th class	19	25	31	38	43	48	51
5 th class	21	26	30	36	42	46	50
Total	86	112	133	162	190	212	232

Table 20. School GPS Sorani (Urban)

	Strength in 2013	Strength in 2014	Strength in 2015	Strength in 2016	Strength in 2017	Strength in 2018	Strength in 2019
1 st class	20	21	26	32	38	44	51
2 nd class	19	23	28	33	39	45	52
3 rd class	18	22	29	35	40	43	49

- The total enrollment of the year 2014 was 1644 while the population of the year was 142700000.
- The total enrollment of the year 2015 was 2014 while the population of the year was 148000000.
- The total enrollment of the year 2016 was 2687 while the population of the year was 154000000.
- The total enrollment of the year 2017 was 2687 while the population of the year was 154000000.
- The total enrollment of the year 2018 was 3058 while the population of the year was 158000000.
- The total enrollment of the year 2019 was 3483 while the population of the year was 159800000.

Research Conclusions

From the above findings it can be concluded that:

- The enrollment rate increases with the population growth.
- The correlation between the enrollment and the population growth is 0.98.
- It is high correlation it shows the strong relationship between the number of enrollments of student and population

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of the study following recommendations are made.

- New schools should be established with the increase in population.
- Facilities should be increased with the passage of time.
- Infrastructure should be increased with the increasing population.
- New rooms should be built in the existing schools.
- Schools should be upgraded with the increasing population.

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